

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - full proposal

Section 1: Applicants

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Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title OSPREY: Open Science Platform for astRonomical discoverY
 Project duration (in months) 48 months

English public summary

Modern astronomical telescopes produce prodigious amounts of data — so much that simply storing or processing it is challenging. Furthermore, many astronomers need to combine data from multiple telescopes to perform their scientific analyses. The resources and infrastructure required to do this limits participation in the scientific process to only the best-resourced scientists and teams. OSPREY will change that, by providing a distributed network of “science platforms” which provides access to and analysis of astronomical data. In this way, we will enable both professional astronomers and the general public to use the products of our most sophisticated and data-intensive telescopes.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 100

Dutch public summary

Moderne astronomische telescopen produceren enorme hoeveelheden data – zoveel dat alleen al de opslag of verwerking een uitdaging vormt. Bovendien moeten veel astronomen gegevens van meerdere telescopen combineren voor hun wetenschappelijke analyses. De hiervoor benodigde middelen en infrastructuur beperken deelname aan het wetenschappelijk proces tot de best uitgeruste wetenschappers en teams. OSPREY brengt hierin

verandering door een gedistribueerd netwerk van "wetenschapsplatforms" aan te bieden, dat toegang tot en analyse van astronomische data mogelijk maakt. Zo stellen wij zowel professionele astronomen als het grote publiek in staat gebruik te maken van de producten van onze meest geavanceerde en data-intensieve telescopen.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 98

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

Astronomy faces a data deluge: data rates from major observatories—such as [LOFAR](#) [1], based in the Netherlands—have increased from a trickle to petabytes per year, with the [SKA Observatory](#) [2] generating over an exabyte per year by the end of this decade. Existing data facilities are overwhelmed.

The Netherlands coordinates the LOFAR Long Term Archive (LTA), with ~50 PB of open-access data under management, and participates in development of the SKA Regional Centre Network (SRCNet), the SKA data archiving, dissemination, and analysis system. SRCNet is noteworthy, as it will deliver a globally-distributed federated data management system.

However, these systems are dedicated to individual observatories. Groundbreaking research generally involves data from multiple telescopes — often, spanning various wavelength ranges. OSPREY addresses this by extending existing LOFAR and SRCNet infrastructure to produce a federated, multi-wavelength data ecosystem. Starting as an extension to the LOFAR archive, we will add support for X-ray data from NASA's archives, and ultimately publish standards and best practices for federation and interoperability across wavelength regimes.

The OSPREY system will provide [FAIR](#) [3] data access, support reproducible workflows and facilitate FAIR and open-access publication of results. Building on open standards, it will strengthen existing infrastructure, enhancing both inclusivity and impact.

Word count SEC31 (max. 200): 200

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

In recent decades, data has exploded in size and complexity: modern telescopes produce petabytes or exabytes of data, cataloguing billions of astronomical sources. Traditional models of data analysis, performed by individual researchers or small teams using their local resources, break down under these conditions: the costs of data transport, storage, and computing are prohibitive. While some of the best-resourced research groups may have access to the necessary infrastructure and the ability to install and maintain the specialist software required, this presents a real accessibility barrier and challenge to open science.

In addition, most astronomical sources emit light at a wide range of wavelengths, and different wavelengths trace different physical processes within these sources. Research with multi-wavelength observations is at the core of solving some of the most fundamental puzzles in astronomy, including understanding the formation and evolution of galaxies; finding and characterizing planets outside of our solar system; and understanding the fundamental nature of matter and gravity. While telescope-specific science platforms are in development and help address the first challenge, they do not provide effective mechanisms for performing multi-wavelength data analyses on large data sets across different telescopes.

The primary target for this work is the professional astronomical research community. This project will enable multi-wavelength science cases on large datasets, democratize access to data, and provide an environment for reproducible research based on open standards and open source software.

Secondary users include developers and maintainers of other data archives. OSPREY will enable easy interoperability with other systems, and, crucially, provide both best practices and software to enable other platforms to join OSPREY's federated network.

Finally, we note the importance of public engagement to the scientific process, and specifically target this community with the development of a "citizen science" project integrated with OSPREY.

Word count SEC32 (max. 300): 292

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

The headline goal of the OSPREY project is to increase the openness of astronomical research by providing access to data, software, and infrastructure to the widest possible community. Further, the OSPREY system will help that community make results available in a FAIR way by providing the tools needed to publish data with appropriate metadata and provenance, and (with appropriate permissions) make it available through the LOFAR LTA and similar facilities.

Astronomy has a tradition of open science, with the [International Virtual Observatory Alliance](#) being acknowledged as a trailblazer in the field of data modelling and interoperability. We will not only build on established standards, but contribute to ongoing development of standards for radio astronomy.

Building on open standards facilitates further interoperability: although not all astronomical data centres will join the federated system proposed by OSPREY, adherence to IVOA standards enables interoperability across the widest possible range of services.

All of the software developed for this project will be open source. This is already the case for the majority of astronomical software, and the PIs are experienced with open source, e.g. of the hugely-successful [Astropy](#) [4] and [Stingray](#) [5] packages.

A key component of open science is building a community. LOFAR already has an engaged community, and we use this in the initial stages of the project to drive development. We will leverage existing relationships with NASA's [High-Energy Astrophysics Archive](#), ESA's [DataLabs](#) and the instrument team for NASA's [Chandra Observatory](#) to ensure alignment with the needs of X-ray astronomy. Citizen science efforts will be built upon experiences as part of the [ESCAPE](#) project, and use the existing open-source infrastructure of the *Zooniverse* project. To engage the wider community, we will organize interactive workshops and hackathons [6,7] based on the successful [Gaia Sprints](#) to promote the project and solicit feedback.

Word count SEC33 (max. 300): 300

3.4 Access policy

The initial OSPREY node will be integrated with and build on top of the existing LOFAR LTA infrastructure. Basic functionality (data discovery, access to public datasets held online) will be available without authentication to all users. Registration will be open to all, and will enable them to be granted access to datasets that are still under a proprietary period or that require staging from offline/nearline (tape) storage. Access to substantial compute or other resources will be moderated through a proposal process which will be integrated with the established process by which access is provided to the LOFAR telescope and associated data services.

The OSPREY software will be open source, and we will support other scientific communities to establish their own nodes. Access to these nodes will be governed by policies set by the infrastructure provider or associated service operator.

Word count SEC34 (max. 150): 140

3.5 (Inter)national ecosystem

Astronomy is an international activity, embedded in large collaborations around observatories such as LOFAR2.0 and SKA (both on the National LSRI Roadmap). Data is generally made publicly accessible (subject to a proprietary period), but analysis is left to individual astronomers or small groups. Increasing data volumes and the importance of multi-wavelength astronomy forces a change: a range of different varieties of "science platform" have been deployed to help address these issues (e.g., the Rubin Observatory Science Platform [8], ESA DataLabs [9], and efforts at NASA).

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What is missing is a layer of standardization and interoperability. As astronomers move from one system to the next, they must adapt to different software, systems, and access policies, and will struggle to access data from other facilities (although IVOA standards and protocols can help). OSPREY will address this by providing the basis for a federated network of interoperable analysis facilities.

Astronomers have recently started developing foundation models: large-scale machine learning models trained on enormous amounts of heterogeneous, multi-modal data sets. As datasets get larger, federated systems like OSPREY will be the only practical way to build these models; OSPREY will integrate state-of-the-art data analysis and machine learning libraries to make this possible.

Word count SEC35 (max. 200): 200

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

4.1.1 Project Structure

The work in this project will be carried out in five work packages. WPs 1 & 2 focus on the development of the underlying software stack and interoperability standards that enable OSPREY, while WPs 3 & 4 build on that system to enable scientific use, including building and training machine learning models, data mining, data visualization and scientific analyses. Finally, WP5 provides outreach & training to the community.

4.1.2 Work Package 1: Data Portal Development (lead: Swinbank; 58 PMs)

WP1 is where the core platform functionality is developed and/or adapted from other systems. It will primarily be carried out by Software Engineers (SEs) 1, 3 & 4, supported by the System Architect & Scrum Master, and drawing on existing software development expertise at ASTRON in both existing LOFAR services and SRCNet to deliver:

- **D1.1:** Analysis of the SRCNet software and its potential application to LOFAR (Month 4)
- **D1.2:** Prototype system providing access to LOFAR data (M10)
- **D1.3:** Deploy & support initial science platform for project-internal use (M16)
- **D1.4:** Platform with support for LOFAR data available to external science community (M24)
- **D1.5:** Support X-ray data (M36)
- **D1.6:** Final delivery placed in long-term hosting (M48)

4.1.3 Work Package 2: Federation and Interoperability (lead: Swinbank; 50 PMs)

WP2 will develop the federated aspects of the OSPREY system — the tools and standards that enable physically distinct science platforms to interoperate with each other. This work will be carried out by SEs 1 & 2, supported by the

System Architect & Scrum Master, and leveraging ASTRON’s expertise with the distributed LOFAR archive, SRCNet, and IVOA.

- **D2.1:** Requirements and initial design for federation system (M18)
- **D2.2:** Key IVOA standards available for use (M24)
- **D2.3:** Demonstrate federated operation between two prototype portals (M34)
- **D2.4:** Osprey federated model & supporting code published; network open to other instances (M42)

4.1.4 Work Package 3: Domain Software & Data Science Tool Integration (lead: Huppenkothen; 25 PMs)

WP3 will help define the science requirements for OSPREY, and will then take responsibility for integrating specialist astronomy and data science tools into that infrastructure to produce a productive environment for the practising astronomer. Integration of specialist software will be carried out by SE5 at UvA with support from the Co-PI and the Postdoctoral Researcher.

- **D3.1:** Science requirements for OSPREY (M6)
- **D3.2:** Fundamental open source science tooling integrated with prototype platform (M18)
- **D3.3:** Integration of X-ray astronomy tooling (M28)
- **D3.4:** User documentation & tutorials for platform release (M36)

4.1.5 Work Package 4: Science Validation & Citizen Science (lead: Huppenkothen; 25 PMs)

WP4 will validate the science platform, focusing on extreme astrophysical transients and black holes, where multi-wavelength coverage in radio and X-rays is of vital importance. This will provide feedback to development in WPs 1–3 and, in collaboration with WPs 3 & 5, produce a set of tutorials for end users. This WP will also prototype a citizen science project on astrophysical transients with the purpose of producing open-source training data for machine learning and data mining applications in multi-wavelength data sets. This work package will be carried out by the Postdoctoral Researcher, in close collaboration with Co-PI Huppenkothen and SE5.

- **D4.1:** Proof-of-concept scientific analyses (M20)
- **D4.2:** Initial tutorials based on proof-of-concept analyses (M24)
- **D4.3:** Prototype citizen science project (M36)
- **D4.4:** Advanced platform tutorials (M42)

4.1.6 Work Package 5: Community Engagement (lead: Huppenkothen; 4 PMs)

WP6 will build on Co-PI Huppenkothen’s extensive experience in facilitating community-building events to engage the wider scientific community with the OSPREY concept using regular workshops and hackathons. This WP will also contribute to the development of the citizen science project described in WP4.

- **D5.1:** Participant-driven workshops to solicit feedback and promote community adoption (M30 onwards)
- **D5.2:** Outreach events promoting the citizen science project to the general public (M34 onwards)

Word count SEC 41 (max. 750): 746

4.2 Team composition

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/Contributions
Dr. D. (Daniela) Huppenkothen	UvA	Data science, x-ray astronomy, building & facilitating communities	Co-PI; WP3, 4, 5 leader.
Dr. J.D. (John) Swinbank	NWO-I/ASTRON	Radio astronomy, software	Co-PI; WP 1 & 2 leader.

		development, project management	
	NWO-I/ASTRON	System architecture, data management	System Architect
	NWO-I/ASTRON	Agile software development	Scrum Master
	NWO-I/ASTRON	Python software development, data management, virtual observatory	Software Engineer #1 (tech lead, WPs 1 & 2)
	NWO-I/ASTORN	Python software development	Software Engineer #2 (WP2)
	NWO-I/ASTRON	User interface & experience design & development	Software Engineer #3 (WP1)
	NWO-I/ASTRON	Python software development, distributed systems, system management	Software Engineer #4 (WP1)
	UvA	X-ray astronomy and data science	Postdoctoral researcher (WPs 3, 4)
	UvA	Open source scientific software development	Software Engineer #5 (WPs 3, 4)

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): 162

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Delay to LOFAR2.0 operations means that science-ready data products are unavailable	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	The OSPREY team is closely engaged with the LOFAR2.0 development team and will work with them to adapt to whatever data products are available. If necessary, LOFAR1.0 data products e.g. as made available through the LoTSS survey [10] would be adequate for testing.
Delay to SRCNet development means that the SRCNet code is not ready for OSPREY at the start of the project.	Likelihood: medium Impact: low	Enough SRCNet prototype code already exists that meaningful early work can be undertaken with OSPREY. If needed, OSPREY will collaborate with SRCNet to develop basic functionality.
Failure of SRCNet to deliver a usable base	Likelihood: low Impact: high	Investigate other potential starting points (e.g. Rubin Observatory Science Platform [8], Sciserver [11])

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System unable to scale to meet demand	Likelihood: high Impact: low	If the community demand is sufficient that the infrastructure funded through OSPREY is inadequate, it likely means the platform is already in sufficient demand that the LOFAR ERIC can adopt it as a useful service.
Slow adoption	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	Conduct hackathons and workshops as part of the project. Additional training engagement events scheduled as needed.
If other partners do not join the network, federated capabilities will not be used	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	Early engagement with other partners (already underway); take account of their needs and involve them in the development effort.

Word count SEC43 (max. 250): 250

4.4 Budget

Position	HOT scale	Institution	Total FTE	Years active	Amount
Senior staff consultancy / Co-PI	HOT 2.1 - 12	UvA	0.50	4	€ 58,265.00
Postdoctoral research assistant	HOT 2.1 - 10	UvA	2.00	2	€ 176,150.00
Scientific software engineer	HOT 2.1 - 11	UvA	2.00	2	€ 200,540.00
Project leader / Co-PI	HOT 2.1 - 14	NWO-I/ASTRON	0.80	4	€ 118,156.00
Software engineer #1	HOT 2.1 - 11	NWO-I/ASTRON	2.00	4	€ 200,540.00
Software engineer #2	HOT 2.1 - 10	NWO-I/ASTRON	2.00	3	€ 176,150.00
Software engineer #3	HOT 2.1 - 10	NWO-I/ASTRON	1.00	4	€ 88,075.00
Software engineer #4	HOT 2.1 - 10	NWO-I/ASTRON	2.00	4	€ 176,150.00
System architect	HOT 2.1 - 13	NWO-I/ASTRON	0.80	4	€ 106,232.00
Scrum master	HOT 2.1 - 11	NWO-I/ASTRON	0.80	4	€ 80,216.00

Material/IT Type	Description	Cost calculation	Total (€)
Storage capacity	Storage for test & development datasets	20 TB stored for 48 months at on SURF dCache at €16.11 per TB/month	€ 15,465.60
Computing time	Cloud systems for test, development, and early operations	3 systems with 8 CPU cores per system operating continuously for 4 years on SURF Research Cloud. 840960 core hours at €0.03362 per core hour.	€ 30,636.17
national symposium/conference/workshop organised by the project itself;	Annual workshops including project team and scientific community	Assumed cost €10,000 per workshop to include travel, accommodation, catering.	€ 40,000.00
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	Participation in international conferences relevant to the development and use of science platforms to learn best practices and present project results.	Based on two people each attending one international conference per year for the duration of the project, at an assumed cost of €3000 per conference, plus an additional two trips to present final results.	€ 30,000.00

Total Personnel requested: € 1,380,474.00

Total Material/IT requested: € 116,101.77

Total budget requested: € 1,496,575.77

4.5 Budget justification

The majority of the budget is allocated to staff costs at ASTRON and UvA. These cover a range of positions, and provide the technical and the scientific expertise that are required to enable the project vision. Their roles and how their time will be allocated is described above.

In addition, the budget contains significant line items for computing time and storage. These are intended to support a prototype system that provides enough computing power and data storage to provide scientifically meaningful functionality, and enough nodes to experiment with the federated and distributed aspects of the project. The project team has experience deploying systems to the [SURF Research Cloud](#), and it is our assumption that the prototype will be hosted here. However, we will also engage with the [SURFcumulus](#) team to investigate other cloud providers.

Knowledge dissemination, both within the project and to the wider scientific community, is critical to this project. We have accounted for this by assuming four annual workshops that include members of the OSPREY team, associated infrastructure providers, and the wider scientific community. In the early years, the content is expected to be primarily technical and focus on the project team; in later years, this budget will be used to support community building and outreach events as described in §4.1. The exact way in which these funds will be distributed will be based on continuous review of what meetings can best serve the project aims.

Finally, we regard it as vital to participate in international conferences, such as the annual [Astronomical Data Analysis Software & Systems](#) (ADASS) series. These provide a venue to learn about other related initiatives, to disseminate our results, and to build partnerships that will form the basis of the OSPREY network.

Word count SEC45 (max. 300): 288

4.6 Impact plan

In order to engage with the professional astronomical research community, we will organize regular tutorials across Dutch institutions and online, also disseminated to the international community using the successful [Carpentries](#)

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format. We will also organize yearly hackathons modelled on the successful [Gaia Sprint](#) format to actively encourage the community to work with the science platform, explore its capabilities and stress-test its limitations. Our tutorials and hackathons will contain structured evaluation elements (e.g. surveys, focus groups) to provide information to the development team.

In order to engage with the citizen science community, we will provide a citizen science project which we will advertise prominently online, e.g. through the [Zooniverse](#) platform. We will release information about this project to the media, and look to build a dynamic and active community of citizen scientists engaged with OSPREY. This will build on earlier work combining professional science platforms and citizen science in the [H2020 ESCAPE Project](#).

In order to engage with the astronomical data provider community, we will advertise our work and build collaborations with them through professional meetings (e.g. [ADASS](#)) and by leveraging our existing professional networks and roles in the SKA Regional Centres Network and [ESCAPE European Science Cluster](#).

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 200

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

Upon completion of this project, the first OSPREY node — providing access to LOFAR data — will be incorporated into the the portfolio of data services operated under the management of ASTRON’s Science Data Centre Operations and offered to the [LOFAR ERIC](#) (European Research Infrastructure Consortium). As part of those services, it will be provided with development effort (for maintenance and potential upgrades), operational effort, and resources to provide support to members of the scientific community, and it will be hosted together with other services provided for LOFAR through ASTRON. The lifecycle of this service will be subject to ongoing agreement between ASTRON and LOFAR ERIC, but we have every reason to believe it will be a critical part of the overall service portfolio.

The OSPREY software and standards will be hosted on the ASTRON GitLab server as described in §5.2. ASTRON will provide ongoing code hosting and management. Development will be continued by the ASTRON team as part of the LOFAR services (as described above), and we will provide support and encouragement to contributors from outside ASTRON with the intention of cultivating a sustainable open source project around the OSPREY codebase. ASTRON will also host and maintain the tutorials and documentation provided for OSPREY.

The OSPREY team has existing partnerships with the SKA Regional Centre Network and the ESCAPE collaboration, and has begun discussions with both NASA and ESA regarding possible collaborations. We aspire to use the OSPREY platform as a nucleus around which a vibrant and self-sustaining international collaboration around data and science in astronomy can form.

Co-PI Huppenkothen has participated in Google’s hugely popular [Summer of Code](#) programme as a mentor for 8 years, and has mentored numerous students during that time. We envision that OSPREY will participate in future Summer of Code iterations under the [Open Astronomy](#) organization in order to mentor junior software developers and build a thriving development community.

Word count SEC51 (450): 314

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

This project will develop software to instantiate and manage a federated network of science platforms, providing easy access to astronomical data and associated analysis services. The end users of the platform will be astronomers (both professional researchers and citizen scientists), but they will interact with it primarily through web interfaces and [REST APIs](#). The software itself will be deployed and managed by system administrators and “devops” teams associated with the service providers.

The project will also develop and adapt data analysis software. This software will be integrated with and made available through the science platform. Where appropriate, it will also be made available to end users directly so that they can download and use it in an “offline” mode on their own systems.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

All software developed specifically for this project will be developed using Git and will be released and managed using a “[semantic versioning](#)” approach. We also plan to adopt and extend third-party open source packages, and — where appropriate — will conform to their established versioning scheme.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

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Software developed in the context of this project (both by the UvA team and the ASTRON team) will follow the [ASTRON Open Source Policy](#). Software released under this policy is normally governed by the [Apache License, version 2.0](#), and that will be our default here. However, since much of this project will be based on established open source packages, we will follow their license terms wherever applicable.

Software will be developed and distributed using the ASTRON GitLab system (<https://git.astron.nl>). In addition, software releases will be made available through the [Research Software Directory](#) and issued with DOIs through [Zenodo](#). We are also aware that some potential users may find GitHub more approachable than an institutional GitLab system, and — depending on demand — will establish a mirror or other way of contributing for GitHub users.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

All software released by this project will be registered with the [Research Software Directory](#) and issued with a DOI through [Zenodo](#). We will also submit descriptions of substantial software packages to the [Journal of Open Source Software](#). Following standard convention, we will provide citation information using CITATION.cff files stored in the code repositories.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

We identify two separate categories of documentation: documentation for the administrators and developers who are responsible for deploying and maintaining instances of the OSPREY platform, and for astronomers and others using those instances to investigate their scientific questions.

For the first category, extensive documentation will be made available in the codebase using tools such as [Sphinx](#), and will be made available online using [Read the Docs](#) or a similar platform.

For the second, science-oriented documentation will be integrated with the platform itself, and tutorials made available through Jupyter notebooks and through online tutorials inspired by the popular [Carpentries](#) approach and open-source template for lesson development and dissemination. Tutorials will be disseminated through a dedicated project website.

Note that the OSPREY team already has experience with these tools: see, for example, the [Stingray](#) documentation. Co-PI Huppenkothen is a certified Software Carpentry instructor.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

We will provide information in the conventional forms (e.g. CONTRIBUTING.md, CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md) in software repositories, and similarly include onboarding and contribution guides on the project website.

7. How will your software be tested?

Both the ASTRON and UvA teams will build on their extensive experience of automatic unit testing and continuous integration using GitLab CI/CD.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

The OSPREY team is experienced in software licensing, and will audit new dependencies as they are added to the codebase and ensure that their licenses are appropriately recorded and acknowledged. Furthermore, we will investigate tooling such as [Tortellini](#), provided by the Netherlands eScience Center, to automate this process.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

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Source code will be managed and made available through using Git at <https://git.astron.nl>. Releases will be distributed through [Zenodo](#) and the [Research Software Directory](#). Software releases will be made available as [Docker](#) (or other equivalent [OCI](#)) container images..

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

During the period of performance of the project, consumers of the OSPREY codebase — developers and system administrators — will be supported by the project development team, while science users will be supported on a best-efforts basis by the UvA science team.

After the conclusion of the project, the ASTRON Science Data Centre will assume responsibility for ongoing hosting and development of the codebase for LOFAR users, and for providing scientific support to that community through the ASTRON SDC Helpdesk. The SDC team will provide support for, and will seek to engage with, the wider ecosystem of science platform users, with the aim of fostering a healthy open-source ecosystem around the OSPREY codebase.

Support for science users of other (non-LOFAR) instances of OSPREY will be at the discretion of the teams hosting those instances.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

As described above, the ASTRON team will assume responsibility for maintenance and ongoing development of the codebase after the conclusion of the project.

Section 6: References

- [1] [van Haarlem, M.P. et al.](#), *LOFAR: The LOw-Frequency ARray*, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, Volume 556, id.A2 (2013).
- [2] [Lazio, J.](#), *The Square Kilometre Array*, *Proceedings of Panoramic Radio Astronomy: Wide-field 1-2 GHz research on galaxy evolution*. June 2-5 2009. Groningen, the Netherlands.
- [3] [Wilkinson M.D. et al.](#), *The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*, *Scientific Data* 3, Article number: 160018 (2016).
- [4] [Astropy Collaboration et al.](#), *The Astropy Project: Sustaining and Growing a Community-oriented Open-source Project and the Latest Major Release (v5.0) of the Core Package*, *ApJ* 935, 2, id.167 (2022).
- [5] [Huppenkothen D. et al.](#), *Stingray: A Modern Python Library for Spectral Timing*, *ApJ* 991, 1, id.39 (2019).
- [6] [Maillart, T. et al.](#), *Computational diplomacy: how 'hackathons for good' feed a participatory future for multilateralism in the digital age*, *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A.382: 20240103* (2024)
- [7] [Falk, J. et al.](#), *How Do Hackathons Foster Creativity? Towards AI Collaborative Evaluation of Creativity at Scale*, *Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (2025)
- [8] [O'Mullane, W. et al.](#), *Rubin Science Platform on Google: the story so far*, *Proc ADASS XXXI*, 535, 227 (2024).
- [9] [Navarro, V. et al.](#), *ESA Datalabs: Multi Mission Science Exploitation and Preservation Platform*, *Proc ADASS XXIX*, 527, 287 (2020).
- [10] [Shimwell, T.W. et al.](#), *The LOFAR Two-metre Sky Survey. I. Survey description and preliminary data release*, *A&A* 598 id.A104 (2017)
- [11] [Taghizadeh-Popp, M. et al.](#), *SciServer: A science platform for astronomy and beyond*, *Astronomy and Computing*, Volume 33, article id. 100412 (2020).

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.